

12M Progress Report

Postdoctoral grant title: “Recovery strategies to improve the performance of martial arts athletes”

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Summary

During the first year of the postdoctoral grant (hereafter project), different work packages and tasks were set. The primary objective was to validate the Recovery Stress Questionnaire for Athletes (RESTQ-36) by Kallus and Kellmann. To achieve this, an agreement was first signed between the authors of the questionnaire (Prof. Kallus and Prof. Kellmann) and the postdoctoral grant supervisor (hereafter project leader) and scientific consultant. In the project, validation of the RESTQ-36 was intended to be conducted. However, Prof. Kellmann suggested elaborating REST-Q 76, which contains 36 questions of RESTQ-36. The translation of the questionnaire was conducted as a forward and backward process (from English to Latvian and vice versa) by six specialists and a linguist. According to the questionnaire manual and advice from Prof. Kellman, the questionnaire was first provided to 100 athletes and later to 300 athletes to assess reliability and conduct a preliminary factor analysis. To be completely adapted, the questionnaire needs to have 600 respondents; the process is still ongoing. During the first year, the ethical letters and the intellectual property strategies were developed between the project leader and consultants. The dissemination of the project was conducted on a weekly and monthly basis through various platforms, including social media, the European Research Night, and workshops for students in the Master's in Sports Science program. The project leader has participated in four international conferences and has also published two scientific papers in peer-reviewed journals indexed in Scopus and Web of Science databases. Another project result was submitting a new project proposal in the national call of the Republic of Latvia (Fundamental and Applied Research).

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1. Objectives for the 1st Year of the Project

- 1) Provide day-to-day operational and ethics management, maintain the agreement between the postdoctoral researcher, scientific consultants, and manage IPR issues to ensure the effective exploitation and dissemination of the project results.;
- 2) To analyze literature data and prepare for data collection in Activity 4.;
- 3) To receive ethical approval from Riga Stradiņš University Latvian Academy of Sport Education (RSU LASE), Latvia and the Akademia Wychowania Fizycznego (AWF) Biala Podlaska, Poland.
- 4) To collect data and analyze the results of the questionnaire.

2. Explanation of the Work Carried out per WP

WP1. Coordination and management

T1.1. Operational issues

During the first year, four international conferences (in August 2024, March 2025, and April 2025) were attended: 1) the international summer school/conference "The Outdoor Sports and Recreation Education Summer School" (OSRESS) held at the Lithuanian Sport University in Kaunas, Lithuania (LSU) in August 2024; 2) 83rd International Scientific Conference of the University of Latvia (LU) in Riga, Latvia, in March 2025, during which were introduced the preliminary results of the RESTQ questionnaire, "A Pilot Study of the Latvian Version of the Recovery-Stress Questionnaire"; 3) During the International Research Week hosted by the Riga Stradiņš University (RSU) in Riga, Latvia, in March 2025, were presented "Monitoring Stress and Recovery: Preliminary Latvian Version of the Recovery-Stress Questionnaire (RESTQ-Sport)"; 4) the 18th annual Baltic Sports Science Society (BSSS) conference held at Vytautas Magnus University, Lithuania and April 2025. A 12-month public progress report was prepared in English for publication in the *Zenodo* repository (current report). Different communication activities, such as emails, Microsoft Teams discussions, and the sharing of documents and files, were conducted with a scientific consultant from RSU LASE, Prof. Juris Grants, and the external scientific consultant from AWF Biala Podlaska, Poland, Assoc.Prof. Artur Litwiniuk.

T1.2. Scientific management

The project leader monitored the project's progress in collaboration with a scientific consultant from RSU LASE and an external scientific consultant from AWF Biala Podlaska. They followed up on the implementation to ensure the completion of all deliverables outlined in the project proposal. The postdoctoral researcher conducted continuous analysis to identify and mitigate risks, providing complete preparation of resources before commencing tasks.

T1.3. IPR management

The IPR strategy (M6) was developed to identify publishable subject matter by registering and continuously updating expected outcomes and foreground-generated content. An agreement was established between the postdoctoral researcher, the scientific consultant from RSU LASE, and the external scientific consultant from AWF Biala Podlaska, outlining the rules for decision-making, IPR issues, and publications, as outlined in the IPR strategy.

WP2. Preparatory measures

T2.. Adaptation and validation of the questionnaire RESTQ-Sport-76.

The validation process was ongoing at the end of the reporting period and took approximately 12 months because it required translation, as well as feedback and answers from athletes and coaches.

WP3. Ethical approval and participant recruitment

T3.1 Ethical approval. All procedures follow the ethical standards of the Declaration of Helsinki.

Two approval letters have been received from RSU LASE (Latvia) and AWF Biała Podlaska (Poland).

WP4. Data collection and analysis

T4. Psychological tests

The validation of the Recovery-Stress Questionnaire requires more respondents, and the process is ongoing.

WP5. Dissemination and communication

T5.1. Dissemination of results

Four reports were presented at international scientific conferences, including the 83rd International Conference of the University of Latvia, the LSU (Kaunas) conference, the RSU Research Week, and the 18th Annual Baltic Sports Science Society (BSSS) conference. A self-activation profile was created within the subject-based repository *ResearchGate* and *LinkedIn*, and regularly updated.

https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Behnam-Boobani?ev=hdr_xprf

<https://www.linkedin.com/in/behnam-boobani-a40673329/>

T5.2. Communication

Dissemination/communication plan (M12) was prepared and implemented. Local seminars, conferences (such as the RSU Science breakfast), and other public events, including poster displays and leaflet distributions (e.g., European Researchers' Night), were attended.

T5.3. Knowledge and data management, and protection

After completing the project, some of the data will be archived in Zenodo and ARGUS, RSU Dataverse, and will remain accessible for at least five years after the project's completion.

3. Preliminary Conclusions

The preliminary Latvian Version of the Recovery-Stress Questionnaire (RESTQ-Sport), based on Cronbach's alpha results, demonstrates internal consistency and preliminary factorial validity. These results were presented at various conferences:

<https://www.rsu.lv/en/project/recovery-strategies-improve-performance-martial-arts-athletes>

4. Main Results

Scientific publications

1. Boobani, B., Grants, J., Glaskova-Kuzmina, T., Žīdens, J., & Litwiniuk, A. (2024). Effect of green exercise on stress level, mental toughness, and performance of taekwondo athletes. *Archives of Budo*, 20, 29 - 40. <https://archbudo.eu/index.php/latest-publication/2024-volume-20/effect-of-green-exercise-on-stress-level-mental-toughness-and-performance-of-taekwondo-athletes-2>

2. “Boobani, B., Kalnina, Z., Glaskova-Kuzmina, T., Erina, L., & Liepina, I. (2025). Utilizing Facial Emotion Analysis with FaceReader to Evaluate the Effects of Outdoor Activities on Preschoolers’ Basic Emotions: A Pilot Study in e-Health. *International Journal of Online and Biomedical Engineering (iJOE)*, 21(07), pp. 61–75. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijoe.v21i07.54291>

Presentations at international conferences

1. Recovery Strategies to Improve the Performance of Martial Arts Athletes, B. Boobani, J. Grants, A. Litwiniuk (Latvia, Poland). 19.-23.08.2024, Kaunas, Lithuania. <https://www.lsu.lt/en/the-international-summer-school-will-be-hosted-at-the-university> .

2. A Pilot Study of the Latvian Version of the Recovery-Stress Questionnaire, Boobani, B.; Grants, J.; Vazne, Ž.; Līcis, R.; Astafičevs, A.; Leja, R. 07.03.2025., Rīga, Latvija (<https://konference83.lu.lv/en/>).

3. Monitoring Stress and Recovery: Preliminary Latvian Version of the Recovery-Stress Questionnaire (RESTQ-Sport). Boobani, B.; Grants, J.; Vazne, Ž.; Litwiniuk, A.; Rajeveska, O.; Astafičevs, A.; Saulite, S. 24-28..03.2025, Riga, Latvia, <https://rw2025.rsu.lv/>

4. Exploring Constructs of the Recovery-Stress Questionnaire through Factor Analysis. Boobani, B.; Grants, J.; Vazne, Ž.; Līcis, R.; Astafičevs, A.; Litwiniuk, A. 28.-30.04.2025, 18th International Conference of BSSS, Kauņa, Lietuva <https://www.balticsportsciencesociety.org/new-page-2>

Figure 1. Participation in the international conference in 2024 (Kaunas, Lithuania). From left: B.Boobani, A.Litwiniuk, J.Grants.

Submitted project proposals

Project proposal for the national call of the Republic of Latvia (Fundamental and Applied Research) - Artificial Intelligence and Psychometric-Based Verbal and Non-Verbal Assessments for Athlete Performance and Well-Being (AIWA), 2025, coordinator: Behnam Boobani.

5. Deviations from the Working Plan

The postdoctoral researcher achieved some positive deviations from the working plan for

dissemination and communication. It is expected that the number of conference presentations and submitted/published scientific papers mentioned in the project proposal (two presentations and two scientific papers) will be higher, thereby maximizing the project's impact. Following the validation of the REST-Q-76, the publication of the questionnaire results was shifted to the second year of the project.

6. Corrective Actions

Based on the suggestion from Prof. Michael Kellmann, the owner and author of the Recovery-Stress Questionnaire (REST-Q), REST-Q 76 was used, which contains 36 questions of RESTQ-36. In cases where appropriate and necessary, the inclusion of all additional and relevant scientific and dissemination/communication activities within the project implementation and their integration into the project work improved the visibility of project results.

7. Plans for Year 2

The submission of two scientific papers to peer-reviewed scientific journals is planned for the next year. Some of the scientific results obtained during the first year will be published in 2025 in peer-reviewed scientific journals included in the SCOPUS or Web of Science databases. The draft version of the article will be prepared late in 2025. The discussion will be held with Prof. Juris Grants and Assoc. Prof. Artur Litwinuik, the scientific supervisor from the RSU LASE, and AWF Biala Podlaska. The scientific and public dissemination of the project will continue to be developed to achieve all planned objectives. The professional profile on *LinkedIn* will be updated with the information on project results for the general public. Information about activities is also posted on the RSU website.- <https://www.rsu.lv/en/project/recovery-strategies-improve-performance-martial-arts-athletes>. Access to the project's scientific results (presentations/posters/papers) will be provided via self-archiving in *Zenodo* and *ResearchGate* repositories.

Project results will be presented at international conferences and scientific popular events, such as the European Researchers' Night in 2025-2026. For these events, exhibits, posters, booklets, and leaflets will be prepared.

Preparing a new European project proposal, e.g., European Research Council (ERC) Starting Grants (STG).

8. Activities for reporting period (M1-M12)

Table 1. List of activities

No	Activity	Result	Status	
		1st year of the grant	Completed	Ongoing
1	Coordination and management	1 report	✓	
		1 IPR strategy	✓	
2	Preparatory measures	1 questionnaire		✓
3	Ethical approval and participant recruitment	2 approval letters from RSU LASE and AWF	✓	

4	Data collection and analysis	1 report		✓
5	Dissemination and communication	1 scientific paper	✓	
		1 presentation	✓	